

Analysis of Over-the-air Frequency and Time Synchronization Requirements for Cooperative ISAC Radio Units with an RF Crystal Oscillator

Robin Lohuis, Erwin Hardeveld, Eric Klumperink

University of Twente, Enschede, the Netherlands

r.lohuis@utwente.nl, e.hardeveld@utwente.nl, e.a.m.klumperink@utwente.nl

Abstract—Cell-free densified networks of radio units (RUs) leveraging cooperative distributed multiple-input multiple-output (D-MIMO) can offer high data capacity per area, low latency, and uniform coverage. As fiber-access cannot be taken for granted in dense deployments, some wireless RUs are required to use over-the-air synchronization (OAS). Distributed networks of cooperative RUs can also support multi-static integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) provided RUs are accurately synchronized.

Frequency synthesizer circuits in RUs are typically first optimized for short-term stability (jitter and phase noise), but long-term stability is also critical to limit timing drift between synchronization updates. At higher radio frequency (RF) carrier frequencies, equal jitter results in tighter phase-noise requirements for frequency references. This motivates the use of RF crystal oscillators (RFXOs) to achieve the required sub-100 fs jitter performance for 6G complex modulation schemes at centimeter-wave frequencies, but such crystals have a worse long-term stability, which we aim to evaluate. Long-term stability can be evaluated using two-sample variances such as modified Allan deviation (MDEV) and time deviation (TDEV). Combining these metrics enables the translation of system-level targets, such as 3.3 ppb frequency stability and 4 ps time error into synchronization-interval requirements.

Using simulation results of a representative frequency synthesizer, we compute the resulting TDEV and design a synchronization loop that improves long-term stability. Our results show that for RFXO-based RUs, our Allan deviation (ADEV) and TDEV requirements can still be met at millisecond-scale synchronization intervals assuming an Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) channel.

Keywords—RF crystal oscillator (RFXO), frequency synchronization, time synchronization, Allan deviation (ADEV), time deviation (TDEV)

I. INTRODUCTION

Future 6G communication systems are expected to rely heavily on technologies such as cell-free networks, distributed multiple-input multiple-output (D-MIMO), and integrated sensing and communication (ISAC). All these technologies require tight time and frequency synchronization between geographically distributed radio units (RUs). Accurate synchronization could even enable coherent joint transmission, high-resolution sensing, and interference management, which are fundamental capabilities for next-generation networks.

In many envisioned 6G scenarios, such as rapidly deployable cell-free networks, RUs cannot always rely on a wired “golden reference” timing signal, but instead require over-the-air syn-

chronization (OAS) to a wireless reference signal, distributed by the distributed (radio) unit (DU). In the 6G Hardware Enablers for Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing (6G-REFERENCE) project, we work on designing hardware enablers to achieve this wireless timing distribution in the FR3 spectrum around 15 GHz [1].

Recent demonstrations, such as drone-based synchronization experiments in [2], show the potential of wireless synchronization while highlighting remaining challenges. This and other phase-locked loop (PLL)-based designs typically lock only to a local crystal oscillator, while orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) processing compensates frequency offset digitally. In contrast, truly coherent D-MIMO requires that the local oscillator itself is phase-locked to a received reference signal at multiple cooperative nodes.

Short-term and long-term stability can be expressed using different metrics, such as phase noise and two-sample variances, which must be jointly interpreted to characterize local oscillator (LO) behavior and evaluate the quality of clock signals. Short-term stability, often characterized by phase noise or jitter, can be managed using high-quality crystal oscillators (XOs). However, long-term stability remains a challenge, as even power-intensive oven-controlled crystal oscillators (OCXOs) suffer from drift. When working with timing sensitive applications as D-MIMO or ISAC, even the slightest frequency offset can reduce accuracy and performance. This slower long-term stability can be improved by (wirelessly) synchronizing the LO of a RU to the clock of the DU, removing any offsets between those clocks. The achievable synchronization accuracy not only depends on the interval, but also on the oscillator performance which determines how much drift can accumulate between updates.

System-level studies motivated several timing and frequency requirements for future systems. Advanced modulation schemes at centimeter-wave bands, which will potentially be used in new 6G standards, require low jitter values below 100 fs. Some ISAC scenarios, such as multi-static radar require a certain frequency accuracy to maintain velocity resolution for Doppler estimation [1]. This required frequency resolution can be calculated using the radar Doppler shift frequency [3]:

$$f_{D,\text{radar}} = \frac{2v_{\text{rel}}}{\lambda} = \frac{2v_{\text{rel}} \cdot f_{\text{carrier}}}{c_0}, \quad (1)$$

where v_{rel} is the (relative) speed in m/s, λ is the wavelength, f_{carrier} the carrier frequency and c_0 the speed of light. It follows that for a minimum velocity resolution of 0.5 m/s at a carrier frequency of 15 GHz the maximum frequency error is 625 Hz or 3.3 ppb, hence we target 1 ppb.

The constraints for coherent downlink transmission in distributed multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) are particularly stringent. For example, for two cooperating RUs, we allow a maximum phase alignment of at most 45° ($\pm 22.5^\circ$ degree per RU). At a carrier frequency of 15 GHz, to keep the loss to a maximum of 0.7 dB due to misalignment, this corresponds to a maximum absolute time offset of 4 ps between RUs. Even tighter alignment in the range of 10° to 30° is required for interference nulling to achieve a reduction of 10 dB to 20 dB [4]. These requirements are challenging, especially when synchronization must be achieved wirelessly in the presence of channel noise.

In this work, we analyze these challenges and develop a framework for OAS suitable for future 6G systems in the FR3 spectrum, focusing on an short-range line-of-sight (LOS) scenarios. The phase noise and two-sample variance metrics are discussed in section II. In section III we will evaluate the long-term stability of LO with a commercially available RFXO. In section IV, the quality of a wirelessly received reference signal will be evaluated. Using TDEV, the required synchronization interval will be calculated, to keep the phase offset between the two clocks below the maximum allowable offset for a D-MIMO and ISAC bi-static radar application. Using simulations of a frequency synthesizer, we extract TDEV characteristics and design a synchronization loop that improves long-term stability in section V. These results provide insight into the trade-offs and design choices needed to realize wireless timing distribution.

II. STABILITY METRICS

A. Phase noise

In oscillator characterization, the hardware and communication communities traditionally use different metrics, each emphasizing different aspects of clock stability. The hardware community typically relies on phase noise, which describes the short-term stability of an oscillator in the frequency domain, and jitter quantifies the corresponding timing uncertainty in the time domain. These metrics are well suited for analyzing PLLs, synthesizers, and crystal oscillators because they directly reflect effects of device-level noise sources such as flicker noise, thermal noise, and reference spurs. Moreover, phase noise requirements directly follow from signal-quality requirements such as error vector magnitude (EVM) and reciprocal mixing since excess phase noise broadens the carrier and degrades constellation accuracy. As a result, phase noise and jitter are the standard descriptors for hardware designers optimizing the instantaneous performance of frequency sources.

(a) Phase noise

(b) Modified Allan deviation (MDEV)

(c) TDEV

Fig. 1. Example phase noise profile illustrating different noise type contributions in phase noise (\mathcal{L}), MDEV (M_{σ_y}) and TDEV (T_{σ_x}). From higher to lower offset frequencies: White phase ($\text{WH-}\phi \propto f^0$), flicker phase ($\text{FL-}\phi \propto f^{-1}$), white frequency ($\text{WH-f} \sim f^{-2}$), flicker frequency ($\text{FL-f} \propto f^{-3}$) and random walk frequency ($\text{RW-f} \propto f^{-4}$). Conversion between phase noise and two-sample variance slopes is explained in detail by Rubiola and Vernotte in [6].

B. Types of noise

Different noise processes contribute to oscillator instability, each appearing in distinct regions of the phase-noise spectrum, as shown in fig. 1a. White phase noise ($\text{WH-}\phi$) originates from thermal noise and broadband circuit noise, producing a flat high-offset region in the phase-noise spectrum. Flicker phase noise ($\text{FL-}\phi$), often described as a $1/f$ process, dominates at mid-offset frequencies and arises from low-frequency fluctuations in semiconductor devices [5]. When white and flicker phase noise are integrated in an oscillator, white $1/f^2$ (WH-f) and flicker $1/f^3$ (FL-f) frequency noise are formed. Random-walk frequency noise (RW-f), corresponding to a $1/f^4$ characteristic, is associated with slow environmental and resonator effects such as temperature drift, mechanical stress, and aging.

C. Two-sample variances

While phase noise and jitter are the main metrics for the hardware community, the communication community often works with (time domain) variances. In contrast to phase noise, two-sample variances provide a time domain view of how clock stability evolves over different averaging intervals as can be seen in figs. 1b and 1c as defined below. These metrics describe long-term frequency stability and effectively capture random-walk and drift processes that phase-noise plots alone cannot express, as two-sample variances have bound values for low-frequency phase noise, even if phase noise increases without bounds for lower frequencies.

The Allan variance (AVAR), $\sigma_y^2(\tau)$ and its square root Allan deviation (ADEV), $\sigma_y(\tau)$ provide a statistical measure of fractional-frequency stability over an averaging interval τ [6]. It quantifies how much the average fractional frequency of an oscillator changes from one interval of length τ to the next. Because it is based on successive frequency differences rather than absolute frequency measurements, ADEV is robust to long-term drifts that would cause traditional variances to diverge. For small τ , ADEV reflects high-frequency noise such as white phase noise, while for large τ it captures slow effects including flicker and random-walk frequency noise. Different noise types produce characteristic slopes in the ADEV representation, allowing identification of the dominant physical noise mechanisms in the oscillator. As a result, ADEV forms the foundation for interpreting long-term stability and for deriving related metrics such as MDEV and TDEV, which translate frequency stability into timing stability needed for synchronization design.

The modified form of ADEV, the MDEV $^M\sigma_y(\tau)$, (fig. 1b) applies an additional filtering step that improves noise-type separation between white- and flicker phase noise. At higher τ , ADEV and MDEV converge. MDEV enables computation of the time deviation TDEV, $^T\sigma_x(\tau)$ using [6]:

$$^T\sigma_x(\tau) = \frac{\tau}{\sqrt{3}} ^M\sigma_y(\tau). \quad (2)$$

The TDEV [7] (fig. 1c) quantifies the accumulated time error over the same averaging interval τ and therefore provides a direct measure of how far two clocks can drift apart during holdover, the time that the local clock runs free without synchronization.

An important concept when interpreting TDEV is the point at which the TDEV stops decreasing with longer averaging. For small averaging intervals τ , averaging suppresses high-frequency noise and the TDEV decreases, meaning that the accumulated time error becomes smaller when integrating the phase error with respect to the reference signal. In this regime, additional averaging directly improves the timing estimate extracted from the wireless reference. As τ increases, slow noise processes such as flicker frequency noise and random-walk frequency noise dominate the oscillator behavior. These long-term processes cause the TDEV to reach a minimum and then increase for larger τ , indicating that drift accumulates

faster than averaging can reduce it, increasing the expected time error due to frequency drift.

For synchronization design, the minimum of the TDEV curve identifies the longest averaging interval that still improves timing stability. Averaging for less time leaves measurement noise insufficiently suppressed, while averaging longer allows oscillator drift to degrade the recovered timing. This minimum therefore sets a practical upper bound on the synchronization interval during holdover, as it marks the timescale at which the local oscillator begins to diverge more rapidly than averaging can correct. By linking oscillator drift directly to timing error, TDEV provides a quantitative criterion for selecting the synchronization-update rate in wireless timing-distribution systems.

TDEV expresses statistically how much the time error can grow over an interval τ . The total time offset ΔT after running freely for a duration τ can be expressed as [8]:

$$\Delta T(\tau) = T_0 + \frac{\Delta f}{f} \tau + \frac{1}{2} D \tau^2 + ^T\sigma_x(\tau), \quad (3)$$

where T_0 describes the initial time offset, $\frac{\Delta f}{f}$ describes the fractional frequency error, D describes frequency aging and $^T\sigma_x(\tau)$ describes TDEV.

To estimate the required synchronization interval in wireless timing distribution, both short-term and long-term perspectives are essential. Phase noise and jitter determine how rapidly the oscillator phase decorrelates over short timescales and therefore set the lower bound on instantaneous timing accuracy. At longer timescales, ADEV, MDEV, and TDEV describe how frequency drift accumulates during holdover and thus define the maximum allowable time between synchronization updates. Combining these views enables a complete characterization of both short-term and long-term oscillator behavior. Consequently, both the hardware-centric and communication-centric metrics must be considered when designing the synchronization strategy and determining the required wireless update rate for coherent distributed systems.

III. RFXO-PLL

Future 6G systems will potentially operate in centimeter-wave bands. One of the potential carrier frequencies ranges is FR3, around 15 GHz. Compared to current 5G-NR FR1 bands, this represents a substantial increase in carrier frequency and places tighter demands on the phase noise performance of the LOs. Phase noise scales with carrier frequency, because the same absolute time jitter corresponds to a larger phase deviation at higher frequency. This effect is captured by eq. (4), where a frequency multiplication factor N results in a N^2 scaling of phase noise:

$$\mathcal{L}(f)_{f_{\text{high}}} = \mathcal{L}(f)_{f_{\text{low}}} \cdot N^2, \quad (4)$$

where $N = \frac{f_{\text{high}}}{f_{\text{low}}}$.

Therefore, at higher carrier frequencies, oscillators must meet more stringent jitter requirements to maintain the same

EVM and constellation fidelity. This is especially relevant for complex modulation formats such as 256-QAM, and even higher constellations which are targeted for future 6G enhancements [9]. To meet these requirements, the phase noise of the XO, which has a lower frequency than the desired output frequency of the PLL, must be improved, or alternatively, higher-frequency XOs may be used to reduce the multiplication factor N in the synthesizer chain [9].

A fundamental trade-off exists between short-term and long-term stability. High-frequency crystal oscillators typically provide superior phase noise at higher f_m , but their low-offset phase noise and long-term stability tend to be worse. This trade-off is illustrated in fig. 2, where the RFXO exhibits better short-term phase noise but degraded low-frequency noise and drift characteristics. The RFXO shows more than 22 dB better phase noise at 10 kHz, when the phase noise of all compared references is normalized to 1 GHz.

(a) Phase noise.

(b) MDEV.

Fig. 2. Phase noise (a) and MDEV (b) of the Viavi (formerly Jackson Labs) 10MHz TCXO [10] and OCXO [11] oscillators, as used in the synchronization experiments by Wentz and Chowdhury [2], compared to the Murata 983.04 MHz RFXO [12], all normalized to 1 GHz.

As discussed in section II, long-term stability cannot be evaluated from phase noise spectra alone. Two-sample variances such as ADEV, MDEV, and TDEV provide a more complete characterization of frequency drift over time.

Figure 2b shows the MDEV for the three frequency references in fig. 2a. The MDEV of the RFXO is well below the requirement of 1 ppb for a broad range of τ , while the lower frequency XOs show orders of magnitude worse MDEV for an observation interval of 200 μ s and below.

In typical PLL architectures, the XO defines the holdover (free-running) performance when the loop is not locked to an external reference. For coherent D-MIMO operation, we target a maximum time error of 4 ps, as calculated in section I. To

keep more than 3σ margin and round, we keep the TDEV of the local oscillator below 1 ps within the synchronization interval. The TDEV of a 15 GHz PLL using a Murata 983 MHz RFXO [12], which we will refer to as a RFXO-PLL, is shown in fig. 3 and is calculated using measured phase noise data from fig. 2a. It can be seen that at a τ of 5 ms the TDEV has reached 1 ps. A larger synchronization interval τ results in a larger accumulated time offset because the linear frequency error scales with τ and because TDEV typically increases for larger τ . Consequently, a trade-off arises between synchronization interval and allowable time error. Shorter intervals relax the oscillator's long-term stability requirement, while longer intervals reduce the required synchronization bandwidth and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

For bi-static radar, we require a maximum frequency inaccuracy of 3.3 ppb. With synchronization, the initial fractional frequency error $\Delta f/f$ described in eq. (3) is corrected. The MDEV in fig. 2b shows that, once the initial frequency offset is removed, the standard deviation of frequency inaccuracy stays below 1 ppb for at least the 1 s interval shown. This demonstrates that satisfying the stricter D-MIMO time-error synchronization requirement, which requires a synchronization interval of 5 ms, implies meeting the bi-static radar frequency-accuracy requirement.

These considerations highlight the tight coupling between oscillator design, carrier frequency, and achievable synchronization interval, and they emphasize the need for frequency synthesizers and PLLs optimized for both short-term and long-term stability in high-frequency 6G systems.

Fig. 3. TDEV-plot of synchronizing PLL around the RFXO, showing a maximum observation interval $\tau = 5$ ms for a maximum TDEV of 1 ps.

IV. WIRELESS REFERENCE

In the envisioned OAS system, the DU continuously broadcasts a pilot tone that serves as a wireless reference signal for the distributed RUs. The DU is assumed to have access to a high-quality wired timing source, such as synchronous ethernet (SyncE) or a fiber-distributed clock and therefore behaves as an ideal reference node from the perspective of the wireless receivers.

At the RU, the reference signal is received through a noisy radio frequency (RF) channel. For the carrier frequencies and bandwidths considered in this work, the dominant impairment in the received pilot tone is white noise originating from the thermal noise of the channel combined with the fixed noise

figure (NF) of the receiver front end. The resulting SNR is therefore determined primarily by the received signal power and bandwidth.

Assuming a simple channel model, the received reference can be described as an attenuated ideal continuous clock signal or pilot tone from the DU, corrupted by additive white noise introduced by the RF channel and receiver. Only additive white noise is assumed, as the dominant noise contribution in a LOS wireless link is thermal and effectively memoryless, while propagation effects do not introduce intrinsic noise correlation at the frequencies of interest (< 1 kHz). This noisy signal can be interpreted equivalently as a reference with additional phase noise. If the total white noise power is split equally between amplitude noise and phase noise, the phase-noise level contributed by the wireless path can be approximated as

$$\mathcal{L}(f) \approx 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{kT}{1 \text{ mW}} \right) + \text{NF}_{\text{receiver}} - P_{\text{rx}} - 3, \quad (5)$$

where kT the thermal noise power density and $\text{NF}_{\text{receiver}}$ the noise figure of the receiver and P_{rx} is the received signal power in dBm, The final 3 dB term reflects the assumption that half of the white noise appears as phase noise. Since only white noise is considered in this model, the corresponding fractional frequency fluctuation spectral density is constant and equal to $S_y(f) = h_2$. This allows direct computation of the resulting TDEV associated with the wireless reference signal, as described by Rubiola and Vernotte [6]:

$$\text{TDEV} = T\sigma_x(\tau) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{8\pi^2} \frac{h_2}{\tau}}, \quad (6)$$

where h_2 is the white phase noise component of the fractional frequency fluctuation function $S_y(f)$. As only white noise is assumed, $S_y(f) = h_2$, and we can use a frequency independent (white) noise level as \mathcal{L} to calculate $S_y(f)$.

$$S_y(f) = \frac{S_\phi(f)}{\nu_0^2} = \frac{2\mathcal{L}(f)}{\nu_0^2}. \quad (7)$$

Importantly, the TDEV of the received reference signal decreases with increasing observation intervals τ , because white phase noise averages down with longer observation intervals. This behavior results in the characteristic negative slope of white-noise-induced TDEV. Consequently, even though the instantaneous phase of the received reference may be noisy, sufficiently long averaging enables extraction of a highly stable timing reference.

Using this model, the TDEV of the wireless reference can be calculated for a given received power and receiver NF, or we can use the required synchronization time from the PLL as determined in section III and calculate the required received power:

$$h_{2,\text{req}} = T\sigma_x^2 \cdot \tau \cdot 8\pi^2, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{req}} = \frac{10 \log_{10}(h_2 \cdot \nu_0^2)}{2}, \quad (9)$$

$$P_{\text{rx,req}} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{kT}{1 \text{ mW}} \right) + \text{NF}_{\text{receiver}} - 3 - \mathcal{L}_{\text{req}}. \quad (10)$$

Filling in the a TDEV of 1 ps and a τ of 5 ms yields a required receive power of -122 dBm. Figure 4 shows the TDEV of this wireless noisy reference with this required receive power. These results show that at observation intervals τ larger than 5 ms, the TDEV of the received signal with white noise is below the requirement of 4 ps.

To validate if this receive power requirement is realistic, we calculate a link budget and the required transmit power to achieve this -122 dBm at the receiver. Following the indoor factory scenario from [1], we can use the LOS path loss model from 3GPP TR 38.901 [13]:

$$\text{PL}_{\text{LOS}} = 31.84 + 21.50 \log_{10}(d_{3d}) + 19.00 \log_{10}(f_c). \quad (11)$$

For a carrier frequency of 15 GHz and a distance of 100 m, the path loss is approximately 97 dB. With a fading margin of 4 dB, this implies a required transmit power of only -21 dBm to achieve the target receive power, which is well within typical transmitter capabilities.

Fig. 4. TDEV of a simple wireless reference model, including only white (channel) noise. A received power of -122 dBm is assumed, to let the TDEV match the target of 1 ps at the same τ as the RFXO-PLL. Less power would require a larger τ , more power allows a smaller τ . The dashed lines represent a ± 3 dB power difference. The TDEV of the unsynchronized RFXO-PLL (fig. 3) is shown for reference.

We can now estimate the performance of a synchronized loop by combining this RFXO-PLL with the received reference using an ideal PLL. In fig. 5 the phase noise and TDEV of the unsynchronized RFXO-PLL, the noisy reference, and this ideal PLL is shown where the PLL has an ideal bandwidth in the range of 100 Hz. In the phase noise plot (fig. 5a), it is shown that the low frequency phase noise of the RFXO-PLL is cleaned up by the reference. In the TDEV plot (fig. 5b), it is shown that the synchronized loop stays below 1 ps.

V. SYSTEM SIMULATIONS

In the previous section, an ideal synchronization loop was assumed. In this section, a practical PLL implementation of such a loop will be simulated. To experimentally verify this synchronization loop, we developed a time-domain stochastic model which models the OAS of a RU. An overview of the simulated system is given in fig. 6.

Fig. 5. Phase noise $\mathcal{L}(f)$ normalized to 15 GHz and TDEV of the RFXO-PLL, the model of the wireless reference and an ideal PLL combining these two.

A. Model description

The model consists of three parts: the receiver, controller, and local oscillator. The model is implemented in MATLAB.

Fig. 6. Synchronization system overview

1) *Receiver*: The first part models the receiver part. A wireless reference signal s_{ref} is received and mixed with the local reference clock s_{lo} , resulting in a baseband signal that represents the phase error ϕ_{err} . The wireless reference is modeled as

$$s_{ref}[n] = \sqrt{P_{rx}} \sin(2\pi f_{ref} \cdot nT_{sim}) + \sqrt{10^{\frac{NF}{10}} \frac{kT}{T_{sim}}} \cdot \mathcal{N}(0, 1), \quad (12)$$

where f_{ref} is the frequency of the wireless reference, P_{rx} is the received carrier power in W, NF is the receiver's noise figure, k is Boltzmann constant, T the temperature. n is the sample index and T_{sim} is the simulation time-step. $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is a Gaussian distributed random number with zero mean and

$\sigma^2 = 1$ to model the channel noise. The simulation time step is set to 1 MHz.

If we suppose that our local oscillator signal $s_{lo}[n]$ has frequency f_{lo} and phase offset ϕ_{lo} , then

$$s_{lo}[n] = \cos(2\pi f_{lo} \cdot nT_{sim} + \phi_{lo}) + i \cdot \sin(2\pi f_{lo} \cdot nT_{sim} + \phi_{lo}). \quad (13)$$

The receiver multiplies $s_{ref}[n]$ by $s_{lo}[n]$, low-pass filters the result, and calculates the phase, which is

$$\phi_{err}[n] = \text{LPF}(\arg\{s_{ref}[n] \cdot s_{lo}[n]\}) \approx \phi_{lo} + \text{noise}, \quad (14)$$

if we assume that $f_{lo} = f_{ref}$. If f_{lo} does not equal f_{ref} , this influence the measured phase error; however, as we will see later, the system can compensate for this frequency error.

2) *Local Oscillator*: The LO is modeled in the phase domain and has three inputs. First, there is a tuning port f_{offset} , which is set by the controller. This controls the applied frequency offset to tune the output phase of the RF clock. The RF frequency f_{rf} , which is fixed in the simulation, is the second input. The third input is a random phase signal that models the phase noise of the crystal reference, ϕ_{pn} .

The crystal oscillator phase noise ϕ_{pn} is modeled with two noise contributions; a Flicker Frequency Modulated noise ($\propto f^{-3}$) and White Phase Modulated noise. The Flicker Frequency noise is generated from Gaussian distributed noise, which is filtered with a bank of first order low-pass filters to generate f^{-1} shaped noise [5]. This noise is then integrated to transform it into noise proportional to f^{-3} . The weights of these contributions are chosen so that the resulting phase noise profile resembles the reported phase noise profile of the crystal oscillator [12] which is also shown in fig. 2a. At offset frequencies above 100 kHz, we assume that the phase noise remains flat at -180 dBc/Hz, as this high frequency phase noise is not significant for long-term stability. As f_{rf} is 15 GHz, the RFXO phase noise converted from crystal phase frequency according to eq. (4).

3) *Controller*: The controller takes the measured phase error ϕ_{err} from the receiver and tunes f_{offset} of the oscillator. This is done at an update interval T_{update} , which is 10 kHz in these simulations. Two control paths are implemented, a proportional path (K_P) and an integral path (K_I) to remove steady-state frequency errors.

B. Simulation Results

We ran the simulation of the system model with a received synchronization signal $P_{rx} = -122$ dBm and NF of 10 dB. We set the gain K_P so that the bandwidth of the tuning loop is approximately 100 Hz, corresponding to the value found in section IV. The value of K_I equals $K_P/100$ to ensure loop stability, as larger K_I degrades stability. The low-pass filter in the receiver is a first-order infinite impulse response (IIR) filter with $f_{-3dB} = 500$ Hz. We applied a static frequency error $f_{rf} - f_{ref} = -200$ Hz to the local oscillator to simulate a frequency error.

The resulting open- and closed-loop time error is shown in figs. 7a and 7b. Some observations can be made. First, when no synchronization is performed, the time error quickly drifts to errors of multiple nanoseconds, as seen in fig. 7a. Figure 7b shows the time error after synchronization, which satisfies the system-level requirement of ± 4 ps peak-peak. On the right-side, a histogram is given, which shows that the time-error is normally distributed.

Fig. 7. Transient system simulations results showing the time error when no synchronization is applied (a), the time error after synchronization (b) and the applied frequency compensation f_{offset} (c). At the right side, histograms show the distribution of values.

Figure 7c shows the applied frequency correction. The mean applied frequency correction is 200 Hz, which shows that the loop integrator corrects the -200 Hz applied frequency error between the reference and the local oscillator. In addition, frequency corrections in the range of ± 100 Hz correct for the detected time deviation.

Figure 8 shows the phase noise and TDEV of the synchronized system. The TDEV of the synchronized system remains below 1 ps, as desired. Compared to the open-loop, the TDEV lowers $\propto \tau^{-1/2}$ after $\tau \approx 5$ ms, thanks to the synchronization loop. In the phase noise plot this corresponds to lower f_m , where the phase noise is close to the noise of the reference signal of -45 dBc/Hz, as calculated in eq. (10). This simulated TDEV also closely resembles the ideal PLL shown in fig. 5b.

For $\tau < 5$ ms and $f > 100$ Hz, the TDEV and phase noise are higher than the open loop system. As the crystal reference noise is $\propto f^{-3}$ and the reference noise is filtered only $\propto f^{-2}$ by the PLL, some noise is added just outside the PLL bandwidth. It is not possible to achieve higher-order filtering near the PLL

bandwidth for stability reasons, but for $f > 500$ Hz the filter in the receiver suppresses some of the reference noise.

Fig. 8. Simulated phase noise (normalized to 15 GHz) and TDEV of the synchronized system showing that the maximum TDEV does not exceed the requirement of 1 ps. The open-loop values are added as reference.

Figure 9 shows additional simulation results where P_{rf} is varied. The maximum TDEV for each of these simulations is shown as a function of P_{rx} . TDEV increases for a lower P_{rx} , but for a higher P_{rx} TDEV does not get lower than 0.5 ps, limited by the stability of the local reference. This shows the resilience of the system to different reference powers, although the achievable TDEV is degraded if P_{rx} is below -122 dBm.

Fig. 9. Worst-case TDEV for different reference powers P_{rx}

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, metrics for both short-term and long-term stability have been discussed and evaluated for a 15 GHz RU with RFXO and OAS. Crystal oscillators typically exhibit a trade-off between short-term and long-term stability. Therefore, in systems requiring both, it is beneficial to use separate references optimized for short-term and long-term behavior. In our case this is an RFXO for short-term stability, while relying on OAS to the DU to achieve long-term time stability.

Using TDEV, we have calculated the maximum allowable holdover time before the loss due to misalignment in truly coherent D-MIMO exceeds 0.7 dB, which occurs if the time offset between nodes exceeds 4 ps. For our 15 GHz PLL with the 983 MHz RFXO, this requires a synchronization interval in the order of 1 ms.

To achieve a minimum velocity resolution of 0.5 m/s for bi-static Doppler estimation, a frequency accuracy of 3.3 ppb is required, which cannot be met by a local reference alone. With synchronization, the initial fractional frequency offset is removed, while a sufficiently low MDEV of the local reference keeps the residual error below the required accuracy over the synchronization interval. The MDEV of the RFXO shows that the minimum synchronization interval is orders of magnitude less strict than for D-MIMO.

Our analysis shows that millisecond-level update rates are achievable for the demonstrated OAS system, with receive powers of -122 dBm. Practical effects such as interference, multi-path propagation, and dynamic fading will degrade the effective reference signal quality and thus restrict the synchronization performance. Hence, experimental validation will be essential to determine how well these techniques can operate under realistic wireless conditions and future work will evaluate this on real IC hardware.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Paliwal *et al.*, “Distributed Radio Specification,” 6G-REFERENCE, Tech. Rep. D1.1, Aug. 2024.
- [2] M. Wentz and K. R. Chowdhury, “Intra-Network Synchronization and Retrodirective Distributed Transmit Beamforming With UAVs,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 73, no. 2, pp. 2017–2031, Feb. 2024.
- [3] C. Sturm and W. Wiesbeck, “Waveform Design and Signal Processing Aspects for Fusion of Wireless Communications and Radar Sensing,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 99, no. 7, pp. 1236–1259, Jul. 2011.
- [4] U. Madhow, D. R. Brown, S. Dasgupta, and R. Mudumbai, “Distributed massive MIMO: Algorithms, architectures and concept systems,” in *2014 Information Theory and Applications Workshop (ITA)*, Feb. 2014, pp. 1–7.
- [5] A. P. van der Wel *et al.*, “Low-Frequency Noise Phenomena in Switched MOSFETs,” *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 540–550, Mar. 2007.
- [6] E. Rubiola and F. Vernotte, “The Companion of Enrico’s Chart for Phase Noise and Two-Sample Variances,” *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 71, no. 7, pp. 2996–3025, Jul. 2023.
- [7] D. Allan, M. Weiss, and J. Jespersen, “A frequency-domain view of time-domain characterization of clocks and time and frequency distribution systems,” in *Proceedings of the 45th Annual Symposium on Frequency Control 1991*, May 1991, pp. 667–678.
- [8] W. J. Riley, “Handbook of Frequency Stability Analysis,” *NIST Special Publication 1065*, no. 1065, Jul. 2008.
- [9] B. Razavi, “Jitter-Power Trade-Offs in PLLs,” *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 1381–1387, Apr. 2021.
- [10] Viavi, “LC XO - TCXO Low Cost 1x1 Inch GPSDO Module - Gen 3,” Datasheet 30193862 900 1023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/literature/lc-xo-tcxo-low-cost-1-x-1-inch-gpsdo-module-gen-3-data-sheets-en.pdf>
- [11] —, “LC XO - OCXO Low Cost Ultra Small GPSDO Module - Gen 3,” Datasheet 30193863 901 0425. [Online]. Available: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/literature/lc-xo-ocxo-low-cost-ultra-small-gpsdo-module-gen-3-data-sheets-en.pdf>
- [12] T. Nomura, “Best-in-Class Phase Noise for Next Generation Connectivity by Super High Frequency Crystal Resonator,” in *2025 55th European Microwave Conference (EuMC)*, Sep. 2025, pp. 350–353.
- [13] 3GPP, TR 38.901, “3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network; Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz (Release 19),” Mar. 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3173>